

FEATURES OF PEDAGOGICAL CONFLICTS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Abstract. *In this article, the conflict is considered as a pedagogical phenomenon, the features of pedagogical conflicts in the primary grades are highlighted, examples of frequently encountered pedagogical conflicts are given and ways to solve them.*

Keywords: *conflict, pedagogical conflict, socialization process, educational process, features of pedagogical conflicts, student, teacher, elementary school.*

Primary school is a practical basis for all students, a foundation. During this period of life, children learn to behave in a team, learn a lot of new things, develop their abilities. The process of socialization to a certain extent depends on the ongoing conflicts.

Conflicts occupy a special place in elementary school. From a psychological point of view, at this age, learning activity is mastered, the arbitrariness of mental functions is formed, reflection and self-control arise, and actions begin to correlate with the internal plan [1]. Such changes are associated with changes in the leading activity, the development of mental processes, the peculiarities of the social situation of development, etc. [2].

Conflict situations in elementary school cannot be avoided, since each child as an individual has his own views, his own opinion and his own interests. B.M. Bekhterev, A.R. Luria, V.N. Myasishchev noted that conflicts are difficult to perceive by children and have a different effect on them. Conflicts can delay the process of socialization of the child in society, lead to difficult relationships with other people.

As E. Erickson noted, a person in his development goes through several universal stages of psychosocial formation or crises. Every crisis has both positive and negative aspects. The further development of a person as a person depends on how the crisis proceeds. If the crisis has passed satisfactorily, that is, a person has been enriched with positive qualities, then his further development guarantees healthy development. And vice versa, if the crisis has passed unsatisfactorily, then it can develop a neurosis and have a negative effect on further psychosocial development.

The fourth stage of personality development falls on primary school age - creativity and an inferiority complex, which covers the period of a person's life from 6 to 12 years. During this period, the child develops the ability to deduce, to organized games and regulated activities. Only now children are properly learning to play games where it is necessary to follow the order. The child becomes more interested in how things are arranged, how they can be mastered, adapted to something. If parents encourage when children make something, cook, needlework and reward for results, then children develop the ability to be creative, skill is developed. Otherwise, they develop a sense of inferiority.

During this period, the child actively observes and imitates adults in everything. Observing what adults do, how they behave in conflict situations, the child develops his position, his own model of behavior. Conflicts during this period become one of the tools of the educational process.

At primary school age, the interaction of the student with the teacher occurs against the background of the desire to be noticed, to please, to please with success in the educational and educational process, to tell about everything. A child at this age tries to be with the teacher all the time, he is open to the teacher, so he usually does not come to conflicts, and if they do happen, then they are based not on the teacher's attention to the student and the student's desire to attract the attention of his teacher.

The important features of this age include the weak development in children of the ability to control their emotions and actions. This is expressed in involuntary reactions to the situation that has arisen. Often situations turn into conflict due to the high excitability of children. At this age, the leading activity of children is still playful, which leads to the possibility of conflicts.

At primary school age, individual characteristics of children are also openly manifested: their reactions to the teacher's remark, their inability to establish positive contacts with peers, egocentrism in assessing academic success, the desire to help the teacher and students, the need for gaming activities, difficulties in adapting to different types of educational classes.

Some features of pedagogical conflicts in primary school:

- professional responsibility of the teacher for the pedagogically correct resolution of the situation;
- participants in conflicts have different social status (teacher-student). This determines their different behavior in conflict;
- the difference in the age and life experience of the participants breeds their positions in the conflict, gives rise to a different degree of responsibility for errors in their resolution;
- different understanding of events and their causes by the participants (the conflict "through the eyes of the teacher" and "the eyes of the student" is seen differently), so it is not always easy for the teacher to understand the depth of the child's feelings, and for the student to cope with his emotions;
- the presence of other students during the conflict makes them participants from witnesses, and the conflict acquires an educational meaning for them as well;
- the professional position of the teacher in the conflict obliges him to take the initiative in resolving it and to be able to put the interests of the student as an emerging personality in the first place;
- any teacher's mistake in resolving the conflict gives rise to new situations and conflicts, in which other students are included.

The educational influence of a teacher is largely determined by the relationship that has developed between him and his students: for some teachers, students are "open" to pedagogical influence, respond correctly to comments, are ready to follow the teacher's instructions, and often consult with him; while others have frequent conflicts, comments cause objections from students, so the teacher is dissatisfied with the students, complains about them to parents, but the relationship does not become more favorable from this.

Communication is the basis of pedagogical activity. It is much more difficult to talk with a child than with an adult: for this, one must be able to adequately assess his contradictory inner world by external manifestations, to foresee his possible emotional response to a word addressed to him, his sensitivity to lies in communication with adults. The word of the teacher acquires a convincing force of influence only if he knows the student well, showed attention to him, helped him in some way, i.e. established an appropriate relationship with him through joint activities.

Meanwhile, novice teachers tend to believe that their word in itself should lead the child to obedience and acceptance of their demands and attitudes.

The conflict often grows out of the teacher's desire to assert his pedagogical position, as well as from the student's protest against unfair punishment, incorrect assessment of his activity, act.

Conflicts of the teacher-student type arise, according to teachers, about:

- violations of discipline in the classroom;
- poor homework;
- unhealthy relationships between students.

From the point of view of students, the causes of conflicts with teachers are:

- insult from the teacher, rudeness, intemperance;
- bias in assessing knowledge;
- uninteresting introduction of the lesson;
- unprepared homework;
- skipping lessons.

One of the main causes of conflicts is the difficulty in adapting a student to a new educational institution and educational activities. The teacher needs to know the children who are experiencing obvious difficulties in adapting, as well as those who feel hidden anxiety and provide them with timely assistance. Otherwise, in such students, negative emotions in the form of a painful stay at school become stable, and already at the beginning of their studies, they form a negative attitude towards learning.

The reason for the difficulty of adaptation may also be the lack of social contact skills with insufficient development of oral speech.

Today, conflicts in the form of ridicule over lagging students or students with special needs predominate in primary grades. Example: there is a physically weak boy in the class, over whom everyone makes fun and mocks. Other students constantly provoke him into an open quarrel. The conflict escalates over time, but is not resolved in any way, because the young man does not want to respond with cruelty to the attacks of his classmates. Those guys who take his side are also persecuted by the leader and his group.

How to resolve the conflict? In some cases, the conflict situation is resolved within the group, without the intervention of outsiders. However, it is important to follow, direct and control it [4]:

- The role of the teacher. A competent teacher can resolve the conflict at the initial stage, excluding its further development. One of the preventive measures is the maximum cohesion of the children's team. Various events and competitions are organized in the class.

- The role of the parent. Not always a teacher in a modern school has sufficient authority among students. Parents also play a role in conflict resolution. The method of settlement in this case depends on the relationship in the family. For example, if the relationship between parents and children is strained, they talk heart to heart, parents simply will not be able to call the child to frankness. In this case, it is better to choose the appropriate story "from life" and present it at the "opportune moment."

A fairly common type of conflict is misunderstanding between the teacher and students. For example, the second-grade student, Nilufar, does poorly in her studies, is irritable and rude in her communication with the teacher. At one of the lessons, the girl prevented other children from

completing assignments, threw papers at the children, and did not react to the teacher even after several remarks addressed to her. At the request of the teacher to leave the classroom, Nilufar also did not respond, remaining seated. The teacher's irritation led him to the decision to stop teaching, and after the bell to leave the whole class after the lessons. This, of course, led to the discontent of the guys.

Such a solution to the conflict led to destructive changes in the mutual understanding of the student and the teacher. It was constructively possible to solve this problem in the following way: after Nilufar ignored the teacher's request to stop interfering with the children, the teacher could get out of the situation by laughing it off, saying something with an ironic smile to the girl, for example: "Nilufar ate little porridge today, the distance and the accuracy of her throw suffers, the last piece of paper never reached the addressee. After that, calmly continue to lead the lesson further. After the lesson, you could try to talk to the girl, show her your benevolent attitude, understanding, desire to help. It's a good idea to talk to the girl's parents to find out the possible reason for this behavior. Paying more attention to the girl, trusting responsible assignments, assisting in completing tasks, encouraging her actions with praise - all this would be useful in the process of bringing the conflict to a constructive outcome.

But in the teacher-student model, the child is not always to blame. It is worth noting that teachers are also not always attentive to students. Bad mood, domestic problems, own ailments - all this leaves a serious imprint on the personality. Many teachers suffer from the fact that they hang negative labels on the child and treat him with prejudice from the very first mistake, without giving him the opportunity to correct it. Example: a girl, a student of the third grade, does not have time in the subject of the English language. The teacher gives her unsatisfactory marks. The child, in desperation, tries to correct the situation, but she does not succeed - she launched the subject too much due to a long illness. The teacher does not want to go into these details, believing that the student should fill the gap on her own.

The class teacher can help solve this problem by explaining the situation to the English teacher, giving details about the health and reasons for the student's lagging behind. You can also talk to the student's parents and ask them to study more. In turn, the English teacher can give additional tasks so that the student can catch up and catch up with her classmates.

Summing up, we can conclude that pedagogical conflicts can be considered in a variety of aspects, but one should not forget about the positive significance of the normativity of this phenomenon. After all, it is not only a source of problems, but also a source of development of the educational process. And even more - a constructive solution to the conflict helps to develop the personality of its participants, in particular students. Conflicts between students can play a positive role in the process of their socialization: understanding how one can and cannot act towards classmates, acquiring the skills to discuss a problem, tolerance for points of view other than one's own, empathy towards an opponent, etc. L. S. Vygotsky noted that the environment does not play the role of a situation, but a source of child development, that only through the relationship of a child with others is it possible for the formation of self-consciousness and its development [1].

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